

Original Research Paper

The Impact of Brand Image and Brand Loyalty on Customer Satisfaction: A case study of Luxury Brand in Thailand

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of this research is to examine the impact of brand image on customer satisfaction: a case study of luxury brands in Thailand. In this research, the researcher will accentuate customer satisfaction and related factors, including brand image, brand ambassador, brand loyalty, service quality dimension, and customer perceived value.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The researcher used numerous components to determine the impact of the brand image on customer satisfaction, including research design, sampling plan, research instruments, the validity of the pilot test, methods of data gathering and procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Findings: This research provides related factors that impact customer satisfaction with luxury goods for a customer currently living in Thailand. This research precisely evaluates those relationships influencing customer satisfaction variables, forming the basis for the study's executive summary. The related factors in this research are brand ambassador, service quality, brand image, brand loyalty, customer perceived value, and customer satisfaction.

Research Limitations/Implications: There are many limitations while working on this research. Gathering information and collecting data from respondents during the COVID-19-19 that occur economic crisis all over the world is a major limitation of this research.

Originality/value: This research study related variables that impact brand image, brand loyalty, and customer satisfaction in a case study of luxury goods in Thailand.

Keywords – Brand Ambassador, Brand Image, Brand Loyalty, Service Quality, Customer Perceived Value, Customer Satisfaction, Luxury brand

1. INTRODUCTION

Thailand's abundant wildlife and flora, as well as its proud heritage, have established it as a flagship destination that is still growing. Understanding a thriving market. Following China's slowing economy, the luxury sector is increasingly looking for new markets. As a result, the sector is now looking to other rising markets including India, Mexico, and, more specifically, Thailand. Thailand offers various benefits to luxury goods companies. Thailand boasts a young, vibrant, and connected populace in addition to a tourism-driven economy. With Thailand's rise, the purchasing power of the premises has increased. As a result, roughly 30% of Thais have a strong desire for high-end goods and services. Thais are also used to traveling and are so exposed to international goods. This globalization pushes investors to concentrate on Thailand's luxury sector. Luxury brands are dominating the rise of the world's top brands in percentage terms, according to data

from Inter-brand's Best Global Brands 2018 study. As Kim and Ko (2012) point out, brand assets are the foundation of this high-added value business. There has been an increase in studies on the marketing of luxury products and services in recent years (Ko et al., 2017), considering the importance of the brand in this industry and its multiple connotations, including the name, logo, symbol, and identity, as well as all tangible and intangible attributes (Prasad & Dev, 2000).

Despite the ongoing COVID-19 epidemic, luxury brands adjust and focus stronger emphasis on their online channels, as the majority of customers prefer to shop for luxury brands through online channels. This significant shift is due to localization, or the adjustment of their marketing strategy to reflect the locality. Many worldwide luxury companies with markets in Thailand have begun to research and adapt to the Thai consumer's behavior during this New Normal era. Exclusiveness is the conceptual key to understanding luxury in marketing.

This exclusivity is maintained mostly through a high price point, but it is also maintained by intentionally restricting sales quantities and outlets. Luxury Goods are defined as very exclusive personal things that show the owner's taste and status in the Consumer Market

Outlook. Apparel, Footwear, Leather Accessories, Eyewear, Watches & Jewelry, and Cosmetics are all included. Luxury automobile data is not displayed here, but it is available in our mobility marketplaces.

Figure 1 The revenue by segment of luxury product in Thailand

Source: <https://www.statista.com/outlook/cmo/luxury-goods/thailand#revenue>

Figure 2 Key player in Luxury Goods market

Source: <https://www.statista.com/outlook/cmo/luxury-goods/thailand#key-players>

Nowadays the competition in the luxury goods market in Thailand has been competitive for recent decades. In this study, the researcher wants to understand the

relationship between brand image and how brand image impacts customer satisfaction. The categories that the researcher focused on are leather goods, appeals, and

accessories. Because nowadays many luxuries brand decide to improve their brand image by seeking brand ambassadors to make their brand become stronger and reach more market capitalization.

The purpose of this research is to examine the impact of brand image on customer satisfaction: A case study of luxury brands in Thailand. In this research, the researcher will accentuate customer satisfaction and related factors including brand image, brand ambassador, brand loyalty, service quality dimension, and customer perceived value within this study.

1.1 Research Objectives

The following details will represent the objective of this study.

- To study the impact of brand ambassadors on brand image.
- To study the impact of service quality on brand image.
- To study the impact of service quality on customer perceived value.
- To study the impact of service quality on brand loyalty.
- To study the impact of brand loyalty on customer satisfaction.
- To study the impact of customer perceived value on customer satisfaction.
- To study the impact of brand image on customer satisfaction.

1.2 Research questions

- Has the brand ambassador had a significant impact on a brand image?
- Has service quality had a significant impact on a brand image?
- Has service quality had a significant impact on customer perceived value?
- Has service quality had a significant impact on brand loyalty?
- Has brand loyalty had a significant impact on customer satisfaction?
- Has customer perceived value had a significant impact on customer satisfaction?
- Has brand image had a significant impact on customer satisfaction?

This study examines five factors that impact customer satisfaction toward luxury goods/brand in Thailand. The primary factors that the researcher focused on are Brand ambassador, service quality dimension, brand image, brand loyalty, and customer perceived value that could influence the customer satisfaction of luxury brands. The outcome of this research would help to understand the impact of brand image that could influence customer satisfaction and the relationship between each variable related to brand image and customer satisfaction.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theories

2.1.1 Brand Ambassador

A brand ambassador is a method used by companies to engage and interact with the community on how to enhance sales (Greenwood, 2012). According to another study, Brand Ambassadors have a role in company communication (Balmer & Gray 2003). Brands to a wider audience the researcher feels that product sales are growing as a result of sales of ad media lines and the majority of ad content emphasizes the spokesperson in such advertisements (Rao & MacInnis, 2002). Furthermore, celebrity involvement on behalf of the organization, according to Yoo and Jin (2013), is comparable to support that favorably impacts the company's image, which is tied to the relationship between the brand ambassador's aims and the organization represented by it.

In this study, companies utilize brand ambassadors to engage and interact with their communities on how they can enhance sales. According to Mudzakir (2018), brand ambassadors are responsible for conveying corporate brands to external audiences. According to MacInnis and Rao (2002), product sales are growing as ad media lines are sold, and the majority of the ad content concentrates on the spokesperson in those advertisements. Furthermore, celebrity participation on behalf of the business, according to Yoo and Jin (2013), is comparable to support that favorably impacts the company's image, which is tied to the relationship between the brand ambassador's aims and the organization represented by it.

2.1.2 Service Quality

According to Taylor and Baker (1994), the shifting business paradigm has placed a premium on service quality. Customers' feedback on service quality is crucial for businesses looking to enhance their marketing strategy (Jain & Gupta, 2004). According to Boshoff and Gray (2004), paying attention to service quality may help a firm stand out from the competition and obtain competitive advantages. Measurement of service quality allows businesses to understand their market position and get a strategic advantage in order to improve their competitiveness (Khan, 2010). Regarding Parasuraman et al. (1988), service quality is the difference between customers' expectations of delivered service performance and their judgment of actual service performance. Service quality, according to Dehghan (2006), is the objective comparison made by customers between service quality and the actual service they receive.

Zeithaml et al. (1985) conducted research in which they offered 10 essential requirements for assessing the quality of client services. Responsiveness, dependability, tangibility, trustworthiness, communication, security, competence, customer comprehension, civility, and service accessibility are among them. Zeithaml et al. (1990) introduced the five-dimensional SERVQUAL scale to assess service quality. Responsiveness, reliability, assurance, tangibility, and empathy are the dimensions. These concepts are more closely related to one another. Service quality is the main component for every client and the customer is the primary person who characterizes the quality (Parasuraman et al., 1993). Thus, according to Lovelock and Wirtz (2004), service quality has many notions and meanings depending on the type of consumer and how they perceive the service quality supplied to them. When the price and other cost aspects are constant, buyers prefer high-quality service (Turban, 2002). Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988) developed SERVQUAL, one of the most widely used models in service research. Originally, there were ten dimensions of service quality, but they were later reduced to five: reliability, tangibles, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

2.1.3 Brand Image

Keller (1993) identified the brand image as customer views of a brand as represented by brand associations stored in their memory. It indicates that brand image is what comes to mind when a brand name is discussed. Customers link the brand with tangible and intangible features; it is frequently reflected by the sensations and thoughts that consumers have in their heads. According to Lee et al. (2009), the brand association quickly helps customers digest information and retrieval when they made a purchase choice since it remembers favorable thoughts and attitudes about that brand. According to Chiang and Jang (2006), brand image has a significant effect on consumer quality and trust. Keller (1993) identified the brand image as customer views of a brand as represented by brand associations stored in their memory. It indicates that brand image is what comes to mind when a brand name is discussed. Customers link the brand with tangible and intangible features; it is frequently reflected by the sensations and thoughts that consumers have in their heads. According to Lee et al. (2009), the brand association quickly helps customers digest information and retrieval when they made a purchase choice since it remembers favorable thoughts and attitudes about that brand.

In general, the brand image is defined as the consumer's impression and trust, as represented in the connections

preserved in their memory. Furthermore, a brand image may aid customers in recognizing their demands and level of satisfaction with a brand. The perceptions that customers have when they come into touch with a product or brand form the foundation of the brand image. According to Aaker (2015), there are three things that may be used to determine a brand's image: the corporate image, the user image, and the product image. According to Chiang and Jang (2006), brand image has a significant effect on consumer quality and trust. Furthermore, a brand image may assist customers in recognizing their wants and happiness with a brand (Hsieh & Setiono, 2004). The perceptions that customers have when they come into touch with a product or brand form the foundation of the brand image.

2.1.4 Brand Loyalty

For at least three decades, researchers have been interested in the concept of brand loyalty, and a considerable body of literature has evolved. Brand loyalty is defined as a strong ongoing commitment to repurchase a preferred product/service on a consistent basis in the future (Oliver, 1997). As a result, despite environmental impacts and marketing initiatives, developing frequent same-brand or same-brand-set buying has the ability to create switching behavior (Oliver, 1997). According to Rehman and Akhtar (2012), brand loyalty by any customer refers to the psychological commitment of the clients toward that brand as well as the repurchase of the brand. As a result of brand loyalty, consumers will not only buy the brand most frequently, but they will also refuse to buy any other brand, even if the other brand has equal or superior quality (Rehman & Akhtar, 2012). Marketing tactics had a significant impact on the creation and maintenance of brand loyalty customers, particularly in markets with high rivalry, high unpredictability, and a decrease in product difference (Mabkhot et al., 2017). According to Chou (2013), brand loyalty may save marketing expenses and strengthen the link between sellers and themselves, reducing the danger of rivals.

2.1.5 Customer Perceived Value

Customer perceived value was defined by Zeithaml et al. (1988) as customers' total estimate of the utility of a product or service based on perceptions of what is received and what is supplied. Furthermore, consumer perceived value is the consequence of a personal comparison between the perceived overall advantages and the customer's perceived sacrifices or costs. According to Parasuraman et al. (1985), only the consumer, not the service provider, can assess whether or not an item or service is valuable, and the concept of customer perceived value is particularly personalized and private. According to Woodruff (1997), customer

perceived value relates to what consumers feel they receive from purchasing and utilizing a product/service, rather than what firms believe their customers value. Swaddling and Miller (2002) defined customer perceived value as a potential customer's assessment of all the advantages and costs of an offering in comparison to the customer's perceived alternatives. Customer perceived value was defined by Kotler and Keller (2012) as "the difference between the customer's judgment of all the advantages and all the costs of a product and the perceived alternatives." Swaddling and Miller (2003) found that, unlike customer satisfaction assessments, customer perceived value measurements offer firms information that helps them make timely choices and eliminate business uncertainty.

2.1.6 Customer Satisfaction

Evans et al. (2006) identified customer satisfaction as a consumer's feeling or attitude toward a product or service after using it. Customer satisfaction, as described by Oliver (1997), is a response that happens when

customers experience a satisfying degree of consumption-related fulfillment when assessing a product or service. Fornell (2001) examined that contentment is directly considered an overall sensation and also suggests that consumers have a sense of how the product or service is similar to their ideal or standard normal. Zeithaml and Bitner (1996) investigated how the level of satisfaction was affected by service quality, product quality, pricing, scenario, and personal variables. Jih (2007) recognizes satisfaction as an emotional response that occurs after the consumer has used the service. According to Gilbert et al. (2004), customer satisfaction describes an evaluation process in which consumers demand the service based on their service experience. Burn and Neisner (2006) investigated that customer satisfaction is based on both cognition and affective reactions to service interactions, and that the evaluation of customer satisfaction is based on both cognition and affective responses to service experiences.

Figure 3. Summary of referencing diagram in this study

2.2 Related literature review between each variable

2.2.1 Brand Ambassador and Brand Image

Wang and Hariandja (2016) conducted a study on brand ambassadors titled "The Influence of Brand Ambassador on Brand Image and Purchase Decision: A Case of Tous

Les Jours in Indonesia." The author utilized brand ambassadors, brand image, and purchase decisions as factors in this study. As a result, brand ambassadors have a positive impact on the company's brand image and customer purchase decisions; thus, the usage of

brand ambassadors as a marketing technique should be expanded. Therefore, the hypothesis has been formulated as follows.

Hypothesis 1 (H1): *There is a significant impact of brand ambassadors on brand image.*

2.2.2 Service Quality and Brand Image

Kayaman and Arasli (2007) investigated customer satisfaction and loyalty in the hotel business and discovered that tangibility, dependability, and empathy all have a substantial positive influence on brand image, but reliability has a greater impact than the other two factors. The researchers discovered that the other two service quality characteristics, responsiveness, and assurance, had no effect on brand image. Ryu et al. (2012) explored the impact of image quality on perceived value, satisfaction, and behavioral intentions, and discovered that there is a substantial positive association between service quality and brand image. According to Selnes (1993), performance quality determines a brand's overall rating. In addition, Ostrowski et al. (1993) proposed in their study of airline service that "positive experience over time following multiple excellent encounters can eventually lead to favorable image." Nguyen and LeBlanc (1998) also showed that service quality was a prerequisite for developing a corporate brand image. They proposed that the better the degree of service quality clients obtained from banks and financial institutions, the higher the level of an organization's brand image would be ingrained in customers' thoughts. As a result, in the service business, client satisfaction is a criterion for determining service quality. Then, the hypothesis in this study has been employed as follows.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): *There is a significant impact of service quality on brand image.*

2.2.3 Service Quality and Customer Perceived Value

Existing research shows that product and service quality affect customer perceived value (Zeithaml, 1988; Bolton & Drew, 1991; Lai et al., 2009; Chen & Hu, 2010). According to Eggert and Ulaga (2002), service quality characteristics (e.g., tangibles, empathy, reliability, assurance, and responsiveness) are positively related to consumer perceived value. Raza et al. (2012) investigated the link between service quality, perceived value, and satisfaction in the hotel business and discovered a positive association between service quality aspects (tangibility, responsiveness, dependability, assurance, and empathy) and perceived value. Higher judgments of service quality, according to Channoi et al. (2013), favorably increase consumer perceived value. According to Ryu et al. (2012), there is no significant association between service quality (tangibility, responsiveness, dependability, assurance, and empathy)

and perceived value. Thus, the hypothesis has been employed as follows.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): *There is a significant impact of service quality on customer perceived value.*

2.2.4 Brand Image and Brand Loyalty

Brand image research has been regarded as the foundation of marketing and advertising research; not only does it serve as a foundation for tactical marketing mix challenges, but it also plays an important role in developing long-term brand equity (Aaker 1996 & Keller, 1993). The brand image was described as customer views of the brand as demonstrated by brand associations stored in their memory (Keller, 1993). Client responses to the brand name, sign, or impression were also captured in the brand image, which served as a signal of product quality. This can be related to Brand loyalty because Brand loyalty resulted in various marketing advantages, including lower marketing expenses, more new clients, and greater substantial trade buying (Algesheimer, 2016; Chinomona, 2016). Brand loyal clients were less price sensitive and willing to pay a higher price for the specific brand in comparison to other alternatives because clients saw distinctive value in the brand (Shin et al., 2019). Then, the hypothesis in this study has been employed as follows.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): *There is a significant impact of brand image on brand loyalty.*

2.2.5 Customer Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction

Turkyilamz et al. (2013) investigated the universal structural modeling method for the customer satisfaction index and discovered a substantial positive association between brand image and customer satisfaction. Amin et al. (2013) explored the impact of customer satisfaction drivers on image, trust, and loyalty, and discovered that there is a substantial positive association between image and customer satisfaction. Ryu et al. (2012) explored the impact of image quality on perceived value, satisfaction, and behavioral intentions, and discovered that there is no significant association between image and customer satisfaction. According to Keller (1993), the image is founded on customers' beliefs about a brand. According to Grönroos (2000), image is a value-added antecedent affecting pleasure and loyalty. According to Fournier and Yao (1997), guests build a good impression of a hotel if they consider one institution is more reputable and trustworthy than another. In a number of ECSI research, Kristensen et al. (2000) found that image had a considerable influence on customer satisfaction and loyalty. According to Cherdchamadol et al. (2013), hotel image has a positive and direct influence on customer satisfaction. Therefore, Aaker (1991) and Rory (2000) found out that when a positive brand image is built, buyers are more likely to be satisfied with the product

and want to suggest it to others. While the product characteristic was not easily defined, Gensch (1978) believed that the brand image had a greater effect on purchase intention and customer satisfaction. According to Graeff (1996), when the consumer's self-image is increasingly comparable to the brand image, customer happiness suffers. Romaniuk and Sharp (2003) discovered a link between brand image and consumer satisfaction. Therefore, the hypothesis in this study has been employed as follows.

Hypothesis 5 (H5): There is a significant impact of customer perceived value on customer satisfaction.

2.2.6 Brand Loyalty and Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction was recognized as a source of customer delight and a critical component of the firm. Customer satisfaction was defined as the customers' joy or discontent as a result of a comparison between the results produced and the client's expectations of the product/service. Customers were not content if the results did not meet their expectations; if the results met their expectations, they were satisfied; and if the results surpassed their expectations, they were delighted (Dimiyati & Subagio, 2016; Kotler & Keller, 2016). Previous research has looked at the relationship between customer happiness and brand loyalty. Several previous studies found that customer satisfaction was a predictor of brand loyalty and had a strong positive influence on brand loyalty (Hidayat et al., 2019; Raduzzi & Massey, 2019). Hence, the hypothesis in this study has been employed as follows.

Hypothesis 6 (H6): There is a significant impact of brand loyalty on customer satisfaction.

2.2.7 Brand Image and Customer Satisfaction

Yu-Shan (2010) investigated the factors that influence green brand equity. Green brand image, contentment, and trust were all investigated. This research study focused on Taiwanese information and electronics items. The findings revealed that green brand image, satisfaction, and trust are all positively associated with green brand equity. Martin (1995) investigated the influence of culture and socioeconomics on global brand image strategy performance. This study investigates the relationship between brand image and performance for consumer goods in two foreign markets. The purpose of this research is to create a conceptual framework that identifies numerous cultural and socioeconomic environmental aspects of overseas markets that are theorized to impact brand image performance. Although, James et al. (2001), found out that brand equity may be controlled at the independent construct level by

delivering certain brand associations or signals to consumers, and these associations will result in images and attitudes that impact brand equity. Henceforward, the hypothesis in this study has been employed as follows.

Hypothesis 7 (H7): There is a significant impact of brand image on customer satisfaction.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

In this study, five theoretical frameworks were used to develop the conceptual framework. The first theoretical framework by Cuong (2020) on the title of the impact of customer satisfaction, the brand image on brand love, and brand loyalty. The significance of branding has been establishing a strong relationship with customers, and it will have the ability to influence customer choice and loyalty. Furthermore, the stronger the bond between the brand and the client, the greater the customer's preference for and loyalty to the brand.

The second theoretical framework by Ismail (2016) on the title of an analytical study on the relationship between brand image and customer satisfaction. The study had been defined brand image as the image that a brand has, and research has shown that various factors influence the brand image. Similarly, research has shown that customer satisfaction is a psychological condition with numerous benefits for both individuals and businesses. Customer satisfaction is determined by different factors.

The third theoretical framework by Tu et al. (2019) on the title of the effect of service quality, customer perceived value, and satisfaction on loyalty. The study mainly focused on these variables service quality, customer perceived value, satisfaction, and loyalty which developed loyalty as a competitive advantage in the market and build a long-term and mutually profitable relationship with a consumer.

The fourth theoretical framework by Mudzakir (2018) on the title of the influence of brand ambassador usage on the brand image of Oppo. The study framework concentrated on the influence of brand ambassador usage on brand image. The fifth theoretical framework by Saleem and Raja (2014) under the title the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, and brand image: Evidence from the hotel industry of Pakistan. The study aimed to test the relationship between service qualities of Pakistani hotels and to scrutinize the causes of customer satisfaction, brand image, and customer loyalty. Therefore, the conceptual framework has been assembled from five theoretical frameworks as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4. The Conceptual Framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The purpose of this study is to determine the factors that impact to brand image toward customer satisfaction which related to brand ambassador, brand image, brand loyalty, service quality, customer perceived value and customer satisfaction in case of luxury brand in Thailand. Beside this study will also determine the level of impact for each variable that affect customer satisfaction of luxury brand in Thailand. For luxury brand in this study will focus on 3 sections which are leather goods, accessories, and apparels. From this study is quantitative research, hence this research will contain many types of analysis such as Cronbach's Alpha, Multiple Linear Regression, and Descriptive analysis. The questionnaire contains of three main parts with a total of 31 items that relate to six variable of this research model, one item related to screening question, six items are related to demographic questions and 24 items are related to measuring variables. The researchers used a five-point Likert Scale to assess the attitudes of respondents and their level of agreement with each variable in this study. The statistical level has been set at 1, with 1 indicating "Strongly Disagree" and 5 indicating "Strongly Agree." Moreover, the Item Objective Congruence (IOC) Index is used by the researcher to

assess the item quality of each question in the questionnaire. To obtain the content validity score, the writers enlisted the help of three specialists. The result for the IOC value was greater than 0.6 for each item, then the researcher performs a reliability test. Cronbach's Alpha with reliability test was conducted to determinate the internal consistency with association of question items. A pilot test was conducted on a small set of 42 samples to validate the measurement items. According to Sekaran (1992), Cronbach's Alpha has a minimum recognized value of 0.6 is acceptable.

Table 1 shows that the researcher utilizes Cronbach's Alpha to determine the strength of association of items to evaluate the scale of reliability. The results represented that the overall variables of the factors that impact brand image and brand loyalty toward customer satisfaction consist of 6 items ($\alpha = .914$). Cronbach's alpha was shown to be significant for the brand ambassador of 4 items is .887, the 4 items of service quality are .895, the 3 items of brand image is .881, the 4 items of brand loyalty is .923, the 3 items of customer perceived value are .916 and the 4 items of customer satisfaction is .883. All factors that impact brand image and brand loyalty toward customer satisfaction are above 0.6, so this can define that they are reliable.

Table 1. Result from Pilot Test

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items	Strength of Association
Brand Ambassador	0.887	4	Good
Service Quality	0.895	4	Good
Brand Image	0.881	3	Good
Brand Loyalty	0.923	4	Good
Customer Perceived Value	0.916	3	Good
Customer Satisfaction	0.883	4	Good

3.2 Target Population, Sample Size, and Sample Procedure

The target population of this research is people who are customers of luxury brands and lived in Thailand. According to Worldmeter.com (2022), which is the

organization that records data on the population in each country represented that the population of Thailand is 70,139,021 (as of Wednesday, June 7, 2022). Nevertheless, the researcher is unable to ensure the target population of people in Thailand that are customers of a luxury brand. Whilst, this research will

utilize the target population as unknown. To determine the sample size of this research, the researcher used Taro Yamane (Yamane, 1973) to calculate with a 95% confidence level. The population of Thailand is 70,139,021 persons from Worldometer.com (2022) recorded the current population based on Worldometer.com (2022) elaboration of the latest United Nations data. The sample size in this study is 399.99 respondents approximately around 400 respondents. The researcher used a non-probability sampling method in this study, which involves non-random selection based on convenience and ease of data collection. The researchers choose convenience sampling and snowball sampling methods to collect information because the respondents will be screened first based on the research objectives, so the sampling will be close at hand and convenient.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive Analysis and Demographic Data

After data collection, the researcher has performed cleaning the data of 462 out of 400, 17 respondents were not eligible for this study, hence the total number of

respondents used in this study was 445 respondents (111%).

4.1.1 Reliability Testing

The researcher made the decision to verify the questionnaire with all 445 respondents to check for any discrepancies or inaccuracies in the variables. To assess and examine a questionnaire's reliability, utilize Cronbach's Alpha test of reliability. Table 2 illustrates how the researchers use the statistical program to calculate Cronbach's Alpha to evaluate how strongly connected a group of items are to each other. The result showed the factors' overall variables of factors that impact brand image and brand loyalty toward customer satisfaction consist of 6 items ($\alpha = .861$). The result shows that all variables are valid and reliable since a value greater than 0.8 implies reliability. The four variables have the highest reliability of .820 composite of service quality of 4 items, brand image of 4 items, brand loyalty of 3 items, and customer perceived value of 3 items. The following is a brand ambassador of 4 items and customer satisfaction of 4 items both of them equally 810.

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha

(n=445)

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items	Result
Brand Ambassador	0.810	4	Reliable
Service Quality	0.820	4	Reliable
Brand Image	0.820	3	Reliable
Brand Loyalty	0.820	4	Reliable
Customer Perceived Value	0.820	3	Reliable
Customer Satisfaction	0.810	4	Reliable

4.1.2 Demographic Data

Table 3, **Gender**: all 445 respondents were distributed in a method that indicated a higher percentage of males with 55.3% which higher than female respondents that contain 44.7%. There were 247 male respondents and 198 female respondents, respectively. **Age**: Most respondent in this research is aged between 40-49 years old with 200 respondents with 45.0%. The following is the age between 30-39 years old with 114 respondents or 25.7%, 88 respondents of age between 18-29 years old with a percentage of 19.8%, 39 respondents of age between 50-59 years old with a percentage of 8.8% and the lowest one is 3 respondents of age 60 years old and above with the percentage of 0.7%. **Education level**: 323 respondents out of 445 have completed a Bachelor's degree (72.7%), followed by 93 respondents with a 20.9% completion rate of a Master's degree, 18 respondents with a 4.1% completion rate of a Doctoral degree or above, 9 respondents with a 2.0% completion

rate of Diploma level, and finally 1 respondent with an educational level in high school level with a 0.2% completion rate. **Employment status**: 430 respondents in this research with 96.8% have been employed. On the other side, only 15 respondents out of 445 respondents with 3.2% were unemployed. **Marital status**: 235 respondents out of 445 with a percentage of 52.7% are single. The following is 201 respondents out of 445 with a percentage of 45.3% getting married. The lowest group is divorce which consists of 9 respondents with 2.0%. **The income per month**: The majority of survey respondents, 183 respondents, or 41.2 percent, earn less than 20,000 baht per month, followed by 136 respondents, 30.6 percent, who earn between 40,001 and 60,000 baht, 45 respondents, 10.1 percent, who earn between 20,001 and 40,000 baht per month, 35 respondents, 7.9 percent, who earn between 60,001 and 80,000 baht per month, and 29 respondents, 6.5 percent, who earn over 100,000 baht per month.

Table 3. Frequency and percentage of demographic data

Demographic Factors	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
• Male	247	55.3
• Female	198	44.7
Total	445	100
Age		
• 18-29 years old	88	19.8
• 30-39 years old	114	25.7
• 40-49 years old	200	45.0
• 50-59 years old	39	8.8
• 60 and above	3	0.7
Total	445	100
Education		
• High School	1	0.2
• Diploma Level	9	2.0
• Bachelor's Degree	323	72.7
• Master's Degree	93	20.9
• Doctoral Degree or above	18	4.1
Total	445	100
Employment Status		
• Employed	430	96.8
• Unemployed	15	3.2
Total	445	100
Marital Status		
• Single	235	52.7
• Married	201	45.3
• Divorce	9	2.0
Total	445	100
Income per month		
• Less than 20,000 Baht per month	183	41.2
• 20,001-40,000 Baht per month	45	10.1
• 40,001-60,000 Baht per month	136	30.6
• 60,001-80,000 Baht per month	35	7.9
• 80,001-100,000 Baht per month	16	3.6
• Over 100,000 Baht per month	29	6.5
Total	445	100

4.2 Descriptive Analysis with Mean and Standard Deviation

Table 4 specified that the highest mean of *brand ambassador (BA)* was “Brand Ambassadors make the luxury brand more reliable” which equals 3.96. However, the lowest mean was “Brand Ambassador who take responsibility for the luxury brand has an impact to brand image” which equal 3.72. For the standard deviation, the highest was “Brand Ambassador who take responsibility for the luxury brand has an impact to brand image” which equal 1.08. Nonetheless, the lowest one was “Brand ambassadors who represent the luxury brand are the key people that introduce the customer to purchase more luxury goods from the luxury brands.” Which equals 0.91. Table 4 specified that the highest mean of *service quality (SQ)* was “The staff of luxury brand appropriately dressed.” which equals 3.93. However, the lowest mean was “The staff of luxury

brand willing to help and communicate to customers with professional skills.” which equal 3.83. For the standard deviation, the highest was “The staff of luxury brand behavior offers customers trust that they will be treated equally.” which equals 1.02. While the lowest one was “The staff of the luxury brand shows sincere interest to help customers.” Which equals 0.96. Table 4 specified that the highest mean of *brand image (BI)* was “Luxury brand image has influenced me to purchase luxury products.” which equals 3.95. While the lowest mean was “Luxury brand has a clear brand image in terms of presenting the character.” which equals 3.87. For the standard deviation, the highest was “Luxury brand has a clear brand image in terms of presenting the character.” which equals 1.01. However, the lowest one was “The luxury brand always improves its brand image in terms of attractiveness to a new generation of customers.” Which equals 0.94.

Table 4 specified that the highest mean of *brand loyalty (BL)* was “I prefer to purchase luxury products from the luxury brand that I usually use rather than other luxury brands.” which equals 3.90. Whereas, the lowest mean was “I am loyal to the luxury brand that I usually purchase.” which equals 3.85. For the standard deviation, the highest was “I prefer to purchase luxury products from the luxury brand that I usually use rather than other luxury brands.” which equals 0.96. However, the lowest one was “I decide to purchase luxury products from the luxury brand I usually use rather than other luxury brands.” which equals 0.94. Table 4 specified that the highest mean of customer perceived value (*CPV*) was “Products from the luxury brand are good for investment.” which equals 3.93. However, the lowest mean was “I believe that money is well spent when purchasing luxury goods.” and “I decided to purchase from a luxury brand because of its superior quality and

services.” which equals 3.88. For the standard deviation, the highest was “I decided to purchase from a luxury brand because of its superior quality and services.” which equals 1.01. Nonetheless, the lowest one was “I believe that money is well spent when purchasing luxury goods.” which equals 0.95.

Table 4 identified that the highest mean of *customer satisfaction (CS)* was “I am satisfied with the services and after-sale services that I received from the luxury brand.” which equals 3.95. Whereas, the lowest mean was “I am really satisfied with the products that I purchase from the luxury brand.” which equals 3.88. For the standard deviation, the highest was “I purchased goods from luxury brands because of the quality of materials and design.” which equals 1.00. On the other hand, the lowest one was “I am really satisfied with the products that I purchase from the luxury brand.” which equals 0.95.

Table 4. Mean and Standard Deviation of scale items

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Brand Ambassador (BA)					
BA1: Brand Ambassador who takes responsibility for the luxury brand has an impact to brand image.	445	1	5	3.72	1.08
BA2: Brand ambassadors who represent the luxury brand are the key people that introduce the customer to purchase more luxury goods from the luxury brands.	445	1	5	3.84	0.91
BA3: Brand ambassadors make the luxury brands more reliable.	445	1	5	3.96*	1.02
BA4: Brand Ambassador has an impact value to the Luxury brand.	445	1	5	3.84	0.98
Service Quality (SQ)					
SQ1: The staff of the luxury brand shows sincere interest to help customers.	445	1	5	3.90	0.96
SQ2: The staff of luxury brand behavior offers customers trusts that they will be treated equally.	445	1	5	3.84	1.02
SQ3: The staff of luxury brand appropriately dressed.	445	1	5	3.93*	0.99
SQ4: The staff of luxury brand willing to help and communicate to customers with professional skills.	445	1	5	3.84	1.01
Brand Image (BI)					
BI1: Luxury brand has a clear brand image in terms of presenting the character.	445	1	5	3.88	1.01
BI2: Luxury brand image has influence me to purchase luxury products.	445	1	5	3.95*	0.95
BI3: The luxury brand always improves its brand image in terms of attractiveness to a new generation of customers.	445	1	5	3.88	0.94
Brand Loyalty (BL)					
BL1: I decide to purchase luxury products from the luxury brand I usually use rather than other luxury brands.	445	1	5	3.88	0.94
BL2: Even if other luxury brands provide greater diversity, I will continue to buy this luxury brand.	445	1	5	3.86	0.95
BL3: I prefer to purchase luxury products from the luxury brand that I usually use rather than other luxury brands.	445	1	5	3.90*	0.96
BL4: I am loyal to the luxury brand that I usually purchase.	445	1	5	3.85	0.95
Customer Perceived Value (CPV)					
CPV1: Products from the luxury brand are good for investment.	445	1	5	3.93*	0.96

CPV2: I believe that money is well spent when purchasing luxury goods.	445	1	5	3.88	0.95
CPV3: I decided to purchase from a luxury brand because of its superior quality and services.	445	1	5	3.88	1.01
Customer Satisfaction (CS)					
CS1: I enjoy spending money by purchasing products from the luxury brands.	445	1	5	3.91	0.99
CS2: I am really satisfied with the products that I purchase from the luxury brand.	445	1	5	3.88	0.95
CS3: I purchased goods from luxury brands because of the quality of materials and design.	445	1	5	3.92	1.00
CS4: I am satisfied with the services and after-sale services that I received from the luxury brand.	445	1	5	3.95*	0.97

Note * the highest mean of each item in each variable

4.3 Hypothesis Testing Results

4.3.1 Multiple Linear Regression of H1 and H2

Table 5 shows a multiple linear regression was conducted to identify if Brand Ambassador and Service Quality significantly impacted Brand Image. The result from Hypotheses 1 and 2 represented that all independent variables utilized to determine influence on the brand image have not coincided and there was no multicollinearity due to VIF being less than 5. The VIF result of both Brand Ambassador and Service Quality is 1.39. Although, R-square was .260 at a 95% of

confidence level. It indicates the independent variables (brand ambassador and service quality) can substantiate the dependent variable (brand image) by approximately 26%. Two factors together account for 26.0% of the variance in brand image, according to the findings, which are $F(2,441) = 77.50, p < .05$. By looking at the individual contributions of each indicator, the result shows that brand ambassador ($\beta = .270, p < .05$). and Service Quality ($\beta = .210, p < .05$) positively significant impact on brand image.

Table 5. Summary of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of H1 and H2

Variables	B	SE B	β	t	Sig.	VIF
(Constant)	1.54	.19	.00	7.90	.000	
Brand Ambassador (BA)	.39	.05	.37	7.59	.000*	1.39
Service Quality (SQ)	.22	.05	.21	4.30	.000*	1.39

Note, $R^2 = .260$, Adjusted $R^2 = .260$, $*p < 0.05$. dependent variable = brand image

Statistical Hypothesis

Ho: Brand ambassadors (H1o) and service quality (H2o) have no significant impact on brand image

Ha: Brand ambassadors (H1a) and service quality (H2a) have a significant impact on brand image

H1 and H2 show the significant level were at .000, which are less than 0.05. The null hypothesis (H1o) and (H2o) were rejected. Consequently, it is obvious that brand ambassador (H1) and service quality (H2) have a significant impact on brand image. Additionally, the standardized coefficient for brand ambassadors is .37 and .21 for service quality. It can be inferred that if brand ambassador and service quality have increased by

1%, the brand image has potentially risen by 37% and 21% respectively.

4.3.2 Multiple Linear Regression of H4 and H5

Table 6 shows a multiple linear regression was conducted to identify if the brand image and customer satisfaction significantly impacted brand loyalty. The results from hypotheses 4 and 5 show that all independent variables used to determine the impact on brand loyalty have not coincided and there was no multicollinearity due to VIF being less than 5. The VIF results of both brand Image and customer satisfaction are 1.33. Although, R-square was .30 at a 95% of confidence level. It indicates the independent variables

(brand image and customer satisfaction) can substantiate the dependent variable (brand loyalty) by approximately 30%. Two factors together account for 29.0% of the variance in brand image, according to the findings, which are $F(2,441) = 92.67, p < .05$. By looking at the

individual contributions of each indicator, the result shows that Brand Image ($\beta = .190, p < .05$), and customer satisfaction ($\beta = .420, p < .05$) positively significant impact on brand loyalty.

Table 6 Summary of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of H4 and H5

Variables	B	SE B	B	t	Sig.	VIF
(Constant)	1.51	.18	.00	8.62	.000	
Brand Image	.17	.04	.19	4.20	.000*	1.33
Customer Satisfaction	.43	.05	.42	9.15	.000*	1.33

Note, $R^2 = .300$, Adjusted $R^2 = .290$, * $p < 0.05$. dependent variable = brand loyalty

Statistical Hypothesis

H₀: Brand image (H4₀) and customer satisfaction (H5₀) have no significant impact on brand loyalty

H_a: Brand image (H4_a) and customer satisfaction (H5_a) have a significant impact on brand loyalty

H4 and H5 show the significant level were at .000, which are less than 0.05. The null hypothesis (H4₀) and (H5₀) were rejected. Consequently, it is obvious that brand image (H4) and customer satisfaction (H5) have a significant impact on brand loyalty. Additionally, the standardized coefficient for brand image is .19 and .42 for customer satisfaction. It can be inferred that if brand image and customer satisfaction have increased by 1%, the brand loyalty has potentially risen by 19% and 42% respectively.

4.3.3 Multiple Linear Regression of H6 and H7

Table 7 shows a multiple linear regression was conducted to identify if brand image and customer perceived value has significantly impacted customer

satisfaction. The results from Hypotheses 6 and 7 showed that all independent variables utilized to determine the impact on customer satisfaction have not coexisted and there was no multicollinearity due to VIF being less than 5. The VIF results of both brand image and customer perceived value are 1.35. Although, R-square was .32 at a 95% of confidence level. It indicates the independent variables (brand image and customer perceived value) can be substantiated by the dependent variable (customer satisfaction) by approximately 32%. Two factors together account for 32% of the variance in brand image, according to the findings, which are $F(2,441) = 128.280, p < .05$. By looking at the individual contributions of each indicator, the result shows that brand image ($\beta = .330, p < .05$). And customer perceived value ($\beta = .320, p < .05$) positively significant impact on customer satisfaction.

Table 7 Summary of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of H6 and H7

Variables	B	SE B	β	t	Sig.	VIF
(Constant)	1.66	.16	.00	10.54	.000	
Brand Image	.30	.04	.33	7.33	.000*	1.35
Customer Perceived Value	.28	.04	.32	7.00	.000*	1.35

Note, $R^2 = .32$, Adjusted $R^2 = .320$, * $p < 0.05$. dependent variable = customer satisfaction

Statistical Hypothesis

Ho: Brand image (H6o) and customer perceived value (H7o) have no significant impact on customer satisfaction

Ha: Brand image (H6a) and customer perceived value (H7a) have a significant impact on customer satisfaction H6 and H7 show the significant level were at .000, which are less than 0.05. The null hypothesis (H6o) and (H7o) were rejected. Consequently, it is obvious that brand image (H6) and customer perceived value (H7) have a significant impact on customer satisfaction. Additionally, the standardized coefficient for brand image is .33 and .32 for customer perceived value. It can

be inferred that if brand image and customer perceived value have increased by 1%, the customer satisfaction has potentially risen by 33% and 32% respectively.

4.3.4 Simple Linear Regression of H3

Table 8 illustrates that a simple linear regression was conducted to identify if service quality has significantly impacted customer perceived value. The result from hypothesis 3 represented that the null hypothesis was rejected. The result of regression stipulated that the model explained 21% of the variance and that the model was significant, $F(1,441) = 114.79$, $p < .05$. With an R^2 of .20 at a 95% of confidence level. The result shows that service quality ($\beta = .450$, $p < .05$) has a positive significant impact on customer perceived value.

Table 8. Summary of Simple Linear Regression Analysis of H3

Variables	B	SE B	β	T	Sig.	VIF
(Constant)	1.99	.18	.00	11.04	.000	
Service Quality	.49	.05	.45	10.71	.000*	2.14

Note, $R^2 = .21$, Adjusted $R^2 = .20$, * $p < 0.05$. dependent variable = customer perceived value

Hypothesis 3

Ho: Service quality (H3o) has no significant impact on customer perceived value

Ha: Service quality (H3a) has a significant impact on customer perceived value

H3 shows the significant level was at .000, which less than 0.05. The null hypothesis (H3o) was rejected. As a

consequence, it obvious that service quality has an impact on customer perceived value. Furthermore, the standardized coefficient for service quality is .45. It is indicated that if service quality rise by 1%, the customer perceived value could be increased by 45%.

Figure 5. The results of the structure model

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary of the study

The research purpose, which is to precisely evaluate those relationships influencing variables of Customer Satisfaction, forms the basis for the study's executive summary. The related factors in this research are Brand Ambassador, Service Quality, Brand Image, Brand Loyalty, Customer Perceived Value, and Customer Satisfaction. The research question that was used conducted in this research was: Has a Brand Ambassador had a significant on Brand Image? Has Service Quality had a significant on Brand Image? Has Service Quality had a significant on Customer Perceived Value? Has Service Quality had a significant on Brand Loyalty? Has Brand Loyalty had a significant on Customer Satisfaction? Has Customer Perceived Value had a significant on Customer Satisfaction? Has Brand Image had a significant on Customer Satisfaction? In this study, the researcher utilized a descriptive analysis to analyze data for the research design. Consequently, this study focused on customers who purchased luxury goods and currently lived in Thailand. For the population, the researcher is unable to ensure the target population of people in Thailand that are customers of a luxury brand. Whilst, this research will utilize the target population as unknown. To gather the number of target respondents, the researcher used the formula by Yamane

(1973) to calculate the sample size. Therefore, the result from the calculation was estimated at 400 targets and 445 responded to the questionnaires that were used for data collection. For consistency and reliability, a closed-ended question was utilized in a structured questionnaire. The collected data can be converted to raw data, which was then evaluated with the support of the statistical program and shown in the form of graphs and tables. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, means, and standard deviations. The study also employed inferential analysis of correlations and regressions for a thorough examination of the variable. For evaluating hypotheses, the researchers utilize Multiple Linear Regression and Simple linear regression. The Simple Linear Regression is utilized to evaluate the level of impact between Service Quality and Customer Perceived Value. Multiple Linear Regression is also utilized to examine the level of impact of Brand Image (two variables are Brand Ambassador and Service Quality) Brand Loyalty (two variables are Brand Image and Customer Satisfaction) and Customer Satisfaction (two variables are Brand Image and Customer Perceived Value). As a result, of the hypothesis testing, each of the five independent variables was considered significant. The results of the hypothesis testing are displayed (Table 9) below.

Table 9. Summary results from the hypotheses testing

Hypotheses	Significant Value	Standardized Coefficient	Result
H1 _o : Brand ambassadors has no significant impact on brand image	0.000*	0.370	Rejected
H2 _o : Service quality has no significant impact on brand image	0.000*	0.210	Rejected
H3 _o : Service quality has no significant impact on customer perceived value	0.000*	0.450	Rejected
H4 _o : Brand image has no significant impact on brand loyalty	0.000*	0.190	Rejected
H5 _o : Customer satisfaction has no significant impact on brand loyalty	0.000*	0.420	Rejected
H6 _o : Brand image has no significant impact on customer satisfaction	0.000*	0.330	Rejected
H7 _o : Customer perceived value has no significant impact on customer satisfaction	0.000*	0.320	Rejected

Note. *P-value <0.05

The results of utilizing simple linear regression and multiple linear regression for the hypotheses testing illustrate the efficiency of factors influencing variables to brand image, brand loyalty, and customer satisfaction. It represents that the most influential factor that impacts

brand image is the brand ambassador. Moreover, the most influential factor that impacts brand loyalty is customer satisfaction, and the most influential factor impacts customer satisfaction is brand loyalty.

Table 10. Efficiencies of factor influence of variables to Brand Image

Rank	Independent Variables	Beta
1 st	Brand Ambassador	0.370
2 nd	Service Quality	0.210

Table 10 implies the ranking of the most significant influence to the least significant impact of independent variables that impact brand image. The research utilized by Beta to evaluate the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. As a result, the independent variable that has the strongest relationship

with the brand image is brand ambassador 0.370, which means for each unit increase of brand ambassador, the brand image will increase by 0.37. Although, it also showed that service quality has a significant impact on a brand image by 0.21.

Table 11. Efficiencies of factor influence of variables to Brand Loyalty

Rank	Independent Variables	Beta
1 st	Customer Satisfaction	0.420
2 nd	Brand Image	0.190

Table 11 implies the ranking of the most significant influence to the least significant impact of independent variables that impact brand loyalty. The research utilized by Beta to evaluate the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. As a result, the independent variable that has the strongest relationship

with brand loyalty is customer satisfaction 0.42, which means for each unit increase in customer satisfaction, the brand loyalty will increase by 0.42. Therefore, it also showed that brand image has a significant impact on brand loyalty by 0.19.

Table 12. Efficiencies of factor influence of variables to Customer Satisfaction

Rank	Independent Variables	Beta
1 st	Brand Image	0.330
2 nd	Customer Perceived Value	0.320

Table 12 shows the ranking of the most significant influence to the least significant impact of independent variables that impact customer satisfaction. The research utilized by Beta to evaluate the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. As a result, the independent variable that has the strongest relationship with customer satisfaction is a brand image by 0.33, which means for each unit increase in brand image, customer satisfaction will increase by 0.33. Whilst, it also showed that customer perceived value has a significant impact on customer satisfaction by 0.32.

5.2 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The hypothesis testing illustrates that there are two variables which are brand ambassador and service quality that has an impact on brand Image. Moreover, there are two factors that have an impact on brand loyalty which are brand Image and customer satisfaction. Although, there are two factors which are customer perceived value and brand image that impact customer satisfaction and service quality and also influence customer perceived value.

5.2.1 Brand Ambassador and Brand Image

This study represented that brand ambassadors had a positive and highly significant impact on brand image. The significant value of a brand ambassador and brand image is 0.000. This suggests that a key factor in a brand

ambassador was the company's consistent initiative to obtain a brand image. This is agreed with Wang and Hariandja (2016) that brand ambassadors have a positive impact on brand image and are able to use marketing techniques to expand it. By observing attentively, the depth of a descriptive analysis of brand ambassadors which was conducted from four questions in the questionnaire that the research has collected, the statistical data shows the means of brand ambassador is 3.84 from four questions. The lowest mean among the four questions is "Brand ambassador who takes responsibility for the luxury brand has an impact to brand image." Which is equal to 3.72 which lower than the average mean. Although this question has the highest standard deviation which is equal to 1.08. As result, it shows that the respondents rate the score quite in the same way, so luxury brands should concern more about obtaining the brand ambassador to make sure that they explore more positive brand image rather than negative.

5.2.2 Service Quality and Brand Image

This study shows that service quality had a positive and significant impact on brand image. The significant value of service quality and brand image is 0.000. This suggests that a key variable in service quality from luxury brands had a direct impact on brand image. This is agreed with Saleem and Raja (2014) service quality has a positive impact on brand image and is able to

increase and improve the brand image and customer satisfaction as well. By observing attentively in the depth of descriptive analysis of service quality conducted from four questions in the questionnaire that the research has collected, the statistical data shows the means of service quality is 3.89 from four questions. The lowest mean among four questions is “The staff of luxury brand behavior offers customers trust that they will be treated equally” and “The staff of luxury brand willing to help and communicate to customers with professional skills” which is the same amount as equal to 3.84 which lower than the average mean. Therefore, those questions have the highest standard deviation which is equal to 1.02 and 1.01. As a result, it shows that the respondents rate the score positive rather than negative, so luxury brands should monitor more about service quality that customers would receive while visiting the shop to make sure that customers would receive a good experience from the brand and it could be the way to maintain and improve the brand image to be more wrathful.

5.2.3 Brand Image and Brand Loyalty

This study illustrates that brand image had a positive impact and significantly influences brand loyalty. The significant value of brand image and brand loyalty is 0.000. This implies that a key variable in the brand image of the luxury brand had a direct impact on brand loyalty that was able to gain more from customers. The result of descriptive analysis of brand image which the researcher collected from respondents. From the three questions that related to this variable, the statistical data shows the mean of brand image is 3.90 from the three questions. The lowest mean among the three questions is “Luxury brand has a clear brand image in terms of presenting the character” and “The luxury brand always improves its brand image in terms of attractiveness to a new generation of customers.” which have the same number more equal to 3.88 which lower than the average mean. Moreover, “Luxury brand has a clear brand image in terms of presenting the character” has the highest standard deviation which equals 1.01. As a result, it represents that respondents give the scores more positive answers. Thus, the luxury brand should maintain or improve its brand image to be more plausible and noticeable to gain more loyalty from customers.

5.2.4 Customer Satisfaction and Brand Loyalty

This research shows that customer satisfaction had a positive impact and significant influence on brand loyalty. The significant value of customer satisfaction and brand loyalty is 0.000. This suggests that a key variable in customer satisfaction from clients of the

luxury brands had a direct impact on brand loyalty. This agreed with Dimiyati and Subagio (2016), and Kotler and Keller (2016) that customer satisfaction can be the joy or discontent of customers toward the brand. If customers had a good experience that meets their expectations, they will satisfy. Customer satisfaction has a positive impact on brand loyalty and is able to increase the loyalty of the brand by satisfying customers.

The result of a descriptive analysis of customer satisfaction was conducted from four questions in the questionnaire that the research has collected, the statistical data shows the means of customer satisfaction is 3.915 from four questions. The lowest mean among the four questions is “I am really satisfied with the products that I purchase from the luxury brand” which is equal to 3.88 which is lower than the average mean. Therefore, the highest standard deviation is “I purchased goods from luxury brands because of the quality of materials and design” which equals 1.00. In addition, it shows that the respondents rate the score in range, so Luxury brands should pay attention more to customers to make sure that they would satisfy while consuming the products and services from the brand. Thus, if a customer had satisfied with the brand, it might gain more loyalty from customers the brand as well.

5.2.5 Brand Image and Customer Satisfaction

This research shows that brand image had a highly significant relationship and positive impact on customer satisfaction. The significant value of brand image and customer satisfaction is 0.000. This implies that brand image has a significant impact on customer satisfaction. As a result, this research agreed with Cuong (2020) who defined the brand image as a set of assets and liabilities, and it connected with the brand name and sign that the assets and liabilities could increase or decrease the value by providing products or services to customers. The result of a descriptive analysis of brand image was conducted from three questions in the questionnaire that the research has collected, the statistical data shows the means of brand image is 3.903 from three questions. The lowest mean among the three questions are “Luxury brand has a clear brand image in terms of presenting the character” and “The luxury brand always improves its brand image in terms of attractiveness to a new generation of customers” have the same amount that equal to 3.88 which lower than the average mean. Therefore, the highest standard deviation is “Luxury brand has a clear brand image in terms of presenting the character.” which is equal to 1.01. In addition, it shows that the respondents rate the score in the same direction, so the luxury brand should pay attention more to a brand

image by maintaining or improving their brand image to become more powerful and trustful to achieve an impact on customers. This would be able to get satisfaction from customers if they have a well brand image.

5.2.6 Customer Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction

This research shows that customer perceived value had a positive impact and highly significant relationship to customer satisfaction. The significant value of customer perceived value and customer satisfaction is 0.000. This implies that customer perceived value has a significant impact on customer satisfaction. As a result, this research agreed with Ryu et al. (2012) which explored the impact of image quality on perceived value, satisfaction, and behavioral intentions, and discovered that there is no significant association between image and customer satisfaction.

The result of a descriptive analysis of brand customer perceived value which conducted from three questions in the questionnaire that the research has collected, the statistical data shows the means of customer perceived value is 3.896 from three questions. The lowest mean among three questions is “I believe that money is well spent when purchasing luxury goods” and “I decided to purchase from a luxury brand because of its superior quality and services.” have same amount that equal to 3.88 which lower than average mean. Although, the highest standard deviation is “I decided to purchase from a luxury brand because of its superior quality and services.” which equal to 1.01. As a result, it shows that the respondents rate the score in same direction. Thus, the luxury brand should be more concern about the quality of product, improve its quality to meet customer expectation and maintain the standard of the products from brand.

5.2.7 Service Quality and Customer Perceived Value

This study illustrates that service quality had a positive impact and significantly influence customer perceived value. The significant value of service quality and customer perceived value is 0.000. This implies that a key variable in service quality is that customer experience from the brands had a direct impact on customer perceived. The result from this research agreed with Zeithaml (1988), and Bolton and Drew (1991) that service quality characteristics (e.g., tangibles, empathy, reliability, assurance, and responsiveness) are positively related to consumer perceived value.

The result of descriptive analysis of service quality which the researcher collected from respondents. From the four questions related to this variable, the statistical data shows the mean of service quality is 3.89 in four

questions. The lowest mean among the four questions is “The staff of luxury brand behavior offers customers trust that they will be treated equally” and “The staff of luxury brand willing to help and communicate to customers with professional skills.” Which have the same number more equal to 3.84 which is lower than the average mean. On the other hand, “The staff of luxury brand behavior offers customers trust that they will be treated equally.” has the highest standard deviation which equals 1.02. As a result, it represents that respondents give scores in several ranges. Thus, luxury brands should concern more about the services that employees of the brand (e.g. Sale Persons, Customer Service Staff and etc.) provide or serve customers by treating customers’ fair and showing more sincere interest to help customers to make customers appreciate the brand.

5.3 Recommendations

Regarding the conclusion, the result of this study illustrates that there is a relationship among variables that had a direct and indirect impact on customer satisfaction in the case of luxury brands. The research’s relevant variables; brand ambassador, service quality, customer perceived value, brand image, and brand loyalty have a highly significant impact on customer satisfaction. Whereas brand image has a strongly significant impact on customer satisfaction and customer perceived value has a dominant significant impact on customer satisfaction. However, the research represents that brand ambassador has the most significant impact on brand ambassador and customer satisfaction mostly influences brand loyalty.

As a result, the hypotheses testing 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 they represented that the null hypotheses were rejected. By this I mean, there are significant impacts on brand ambassador, service quality, and customer perceived value, brand image, brand loyalty, and customer satisfaction from customers who purchase luxury goods and currently lived in Thailand. Additionally, the globalization of the entertainment sector through television programs and online video material has altered customer tastes for luxury items. Due to many global social, economic, and cultural developments, there has been a noticeable rise in the demand for luxury products. The type, distribution channel, business, and region are the divisions used to divide the global market for luxury goods. The jewelry and watch category are leading the global luxury goods market in terms of type, because of a rising emphasis on evolving lifestyles and the newest trends in clothing.

Eventually, luxury brands should concern more with the services and brand image of the brands because this can impact customers directly. By this I mean, for services, it is able to impact directly because when customers visit to shop, they will get any experiences from the staff of the brand directly. If staff provide bad service or treat customers in a negative way, customers would receive a bad experience from the brand and it could be word of mouth on social media easily.

5.4 Further Study

According to this research, there are only six variables which are brand ambassador, service quality, and customer perceived value, brand image, and brand loyalty that impact to customer satisfaction of customers who purchases luxury goods and currently live in Thailand. Due to the limitation of collecting respondents they only have a few weeks to achieve the goal. For further study, it would be able to apply more variables that relate to this topic by finding more related articles to apply in further study. Additionally, further study should be done using bigger sample size and population to enhance the generalizability and reliability of the findings. Lastly, this study would be able to apply in the future because the trends of luxury goods are normally fast and go.

REFERENCES

1. Aaker, D. A. (1996). Measuring Brand Equity Across Products and Markets. *California Management Review*, 38(3), 102–120. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41165845>
2. Algesheimer, R., Dholakia, U. M., & Herrmann, A. (2005). The social influence of brand community: Evidence from European car clubs. *Journal of Marketing*, 69(3), 19–34. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.69.3.19.66363>
3. Atwal, G., & Williams, A. (2009). Luxury brand marketing – The experience is everything! *Journal of Brand Management*, 16(5-6), 338-346. <https://doi.org/10.1057/bm.2008.48>
4. Aymar, R., & Joseph, E. M. (2019). Customers satisfaction and brand loyalty at McDonalds Maroc. *African Journal of Marketing Management*, 11(3), 21-34. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ajmm2019.0599>
5. Balmer, J. M., & Gray, E. R. (2003). Corporate brands: What are they? What of them? *European Journal of Marketing*, 37(7/8), 972-997. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090560310477627>
6. Boshoff, C. & Gray, B. (2004). The Relationships between Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Buying Intentions in the Private Hospital Industry. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 35(4), 27–37.
7. Bolton, R. & Drew, J. (1991). A Longitudinal Analysis of the Impact of Service Changes on Customer Attitudes. *Journal of Marketing*, 55(1), 1-10.
8. Burns, D. and Neisner, L. (2006). Customer satisfaction in a retail setting: The contribution of emotion. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, 34(1), 49 - 66.
9. Channoi, R., Clemes, M. D. & Dean, D. (2013, November). A Comprehensive Hierarchical Model of Resort Hotel Stays in Thailand: An Empirical Analysis. *Proceedings of 23rd International Business Research Conference, Marriott Hotel, Melbourne, Australia*.
10. Chen, P., & Hu, H. (2010). How determinant attributes of service quality influence customer-perceived value. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 22(4), 535-551. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596111011042730>
11. Chen, Y. (2009). The drivers of green brand equity: green brand image, green satisfaction, and green trust. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 93(2), 307-319. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-009-0223-9>
12. Chiang, C., & Jang, S. S. (2007). The effects of perceived price and brand image on value and purchase intention: Leisure travelers' attitudes toward online hotel booking. *Journal of Hospitality & Leisure Marketing*, 15(3), 49-69. https://doi.org/10.1300/j150v15n03_04
13. Chinomona, R. (2016). Brand communication, brand image and brand trust as antecedents of brand loyalty in Gauteng Province of South Africa. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 7(1), 124-139.
14. Chou, C.-M. (2013). Factors Affecting Brand Identification and Loyalty in Online Community. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 3(8), 674–680. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajibm.2013.38076>
15. Cuong, Dam. (2020). The Impact of Customer Satisfaction, Brand Image on Brand Love and Brand Loyalty. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*. 12.3151-3159. <https://doi.org/10.13106/>
16. Dehghan, A. (2006). Relationship between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction. Luella University of Technology, *Master Thesis*.

17. Dimiyati, M., & Subagio, N. A. (2016). Impact of service quality, price, and brand on loyalty with the mediation of customer satisfaction on POS Ekspres in East Java. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2016.v7n4p74>
18. Eggert, A., & Ulaga, W. (2002). Customer perceived value: A substitute for satisfaction in business markets? *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 17(2/3), 107-118. <https://doi.org/10.1108/08858620210419754>
19. Evans, M. & Jamal, A. & Foxall, G. (2006). *Consumer Behavior (2nd edition)*. London: Wiley.
20. Faircloth, J. B., Capella, L. M., & Alford, B. L. (2001). The effect of brand attitude and brand image on brand equity. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 9(3), 61-75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10696679.2001.11501897>
21. Fornell, C. (2001). The Score of Satisfaction. *Harvard Business Review*, 79, 120-121.
22. Fournier, S., & Yao, J. L. (1997). Reviving brand loyalty: A reconceptualization within the framework of consumer-brand relationships. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 14(5), 451-472. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0167-8116\(97\)00021-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0167-8116(97)00021-9)
23. Gensch, DC. (1978). Image-measurement segmentation. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 15(3), 384-394. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224377801500309>
24. Gilbert, G. R., Veloutsou, C., Goode, M. M., & Moutinho, L. (2004). Measuring customer satisfaction in the fast food industry: A cross-national approach. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 18(5), 371-383. <https://doi.org/10.1108/08876040410548294>
25. Graeff, T. R. (1996). Image congruence effects on product evaluations: The role of self-monitoring and public/private consumption. *Psychology and Marketing*, 13(5), 481-499. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(sici\)1520-6793\(199608\)13:5<481::aid-mar3>3.0.co;2-5](https://doi.org/10.1002/(sici)1520-6793(199608)13:5<481::aid-mar3>3.0.co;2-5)
26. Grönroos, C. (2000). *Service management and marketing: A customer relationship management approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
27. Hidayat, A., Adanti, A. P., Darmawan, A., & Setyaning, A. N. (2019). Factors influencing Indonesian customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in local fast-food restaurant. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 11(3), 131. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijms.v11n3p131>
28. Hsieh, S., Lu, C., & Lu, Y. (2018). A study on the relationship among brand image, service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty – Taking ‘the Bao Wei Zhen catering team’ as an empirical study. *KnE Social Sciences*, 3(10). <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v3i10.3512>
29. Ismail, M. (2016). An analytical study on Relationship between Brand Image and Customer Satisfaction. *ISBR Management Journal*, 1(2), 1-11.
30. Jain, S. K., & Gupta, G. (2004). Measuring service quality: Servqual vs. Servperf scales. Vikalpa: *The Journal for Decision Makers*, 29(2), 25-38. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0256090920040203>
31. Jih, W. (. (2009). Service features, customer convenience, and shopping intention in the context of mobile commerce. *Comparison-Shopping Services and Agent Designs*, 134-150. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-59904-978-6.ch009>
32. Kawachart, P. & Sriboonjit, J. (2013). Customer Satisfaction with Luxury Hotel in Bangkok: The Influence of Housekeeping Service Quality. In *20th Annual European Real Estate Society Conference. ERES: Conference*. Vienna, Austria. <http://eres.scix.net>
33. Kayaman, R. and Arasli, H. (2007), "Customer based brand equity: evidence from the hotel industry", *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 17(1), 92-109. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604520710720692>
34. Keller, K. L. (1993). Conceptualizing, measuring, and managing customer-based brand equity. *Journal of Marketing*, 57(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1252054>
35. Khan, M. A. (2010). An empirical assessment of service quality of cellular mobile telephone operators in Pakistan. *Asian Social Science*, 6(10). <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v6n10p164>
36. Kim, A. J., & Ko, E. (2012). Do social media marketing activities enhance customer equity? An empirical study of luxury fashion brand. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(10), 1480-1486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.10.014>
37. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2012). *Marketing management*. Pearson College Division.
38. Kristensen, K., Martensen, A., & Gronholdt, L. (2000). Customer satisfaction measurement at post Denmark: Results of application of the European

- customer satisfaction index methodology. *Total Quality Management*, 11(7), 1007-1015. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09544120050135533>
39. Lai, F., Griffin, M., & Babin, B. J. (2009). How quality, value, image, and satisfaction create loyalty at a Chinese telecom. *Journal of Business Research*, 62(10), 980-986. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2008.10.015>
40. Lea-Greenwood, G. (2013). *Fashion marketing communications*. John Wiley & Sons.
41. Michael S. W. Lee, Denise Conroy, and Judith Motion (2009), "Brand Avoidance: a Negative Promises Perspective", in *NA -Advances in Consumer Research* Volume 36, eds. Ann L. McGill and Sharon Shavitt, Duluth, MN :Association for Consumer Research, 421-429.
42. Liu, F., Li, J., Mizerski, D., & Soh, H. (2012). Self-congruity, brand attitude, and brand loyalty: A study on luxury brands. *European Journal of Marketing*, 46(7/8), 922-937. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090561211230098>
43. Lovelock, C. H., & Wirtz, J. (2014). *Services marketing: People, technology, strategy*. Pearson College Division.
44. Mabkhot, H. A., Hasnizam, & Salleh, S. M. (2017). *The Influence of Brand Image and Brand Personality on Brand Loyalty, Mediating by Brand Trust: An Empirical Study*. *Journal Pengurusan*, 50, 1-18.
45. Macinnis, D. J., Rao, A. G., & Weiss, A. M. (2002). Assessing when increased media weight of real-world advertisements helps sales. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 39(4), 391-407. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkr.39.4.391.19118>.
46. Mai, Dam & Cuong, Dam. (2021). Relationships between Service Quality, Brand Image, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty. *Journal of Asian Finance Economics and Business*, 8(3), 585-593. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13106/>
47. Morgan, R. P. (2000). A consumer-oriented framework of brand equity and loyalty. *International Journal of Market Research*, 42(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1177/147078530004200105>
48. Roth, M. S. (1995). The effects of culture and socioeconomics on the performance of global brand image strategies. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 32(2), 163-175. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002224379503200204>
49. Mudzakir, F. (2018). The influence of brand ambassador usage toward brand image of Oppo. *Industrial Research Workshop and National Seminar (IRONS)*, 648-654. <https://doi.org/10.35313/irwns.v9i0.1109>
50. Nguyen, N., & LeBlanc, G. (1998). The mediating role of corporate image on customers' retention decisions: An investigation in financial services. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 16(2), 52-65. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02652329810206707>
51. Oliver, R. L. (2014). *Satisfaction: A behavioral perspective on the consumer: A behavioral perspective on the consumer*. Routledge.
52. Ostrowski, P. L., O'Brien, T. V., & Gordon, G. L. (1993). Service quality and customer loyalty in the commercial airline industry. *Journal of Travel Research*, 32(2), 16-24. <https://doi.org/10.1177/004728759303200203>
53. Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1985). A conceptual model of service quality and its implications for future research. *Journal of Marketing*, 49(4), 41. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1251430>
54. Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A. & Berry, L. L. (1988). SERVQUAL-a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64 (1), 12-40.
55. Parasuraman, A., Berry, L. L., & Zeithaml, V. A. (1991). Refinement and reassessment of the SERVQUAL scale. *Journal of Retailing*, 67(4), 420-450.
56. Park, C. W., Jaworski, B. J., & MacInnis, D. J. (1986). Strategic brand concept-image management. *Journal of Marketing*, 50(4), 135. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1251291>
57. Prasad, K., & Dev, C. S. (2000). Managing hotel brand equity. *Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly*, 41(3), 22-31. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001088040004100314>
58. Raza, M. A., Awan, A. N., & Bukhari, K. (2012). Relationship between Service Quality, Perceived Value, Satisfaction and Revisit Intention in Hotel Industry. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 4(8), 788-805.
59. Rehman, A., Zia-ur-rehman, M., & Akhtar, W. (2012). Factors affecting Brand Loyalty: a perspective of fast-food restaurants. *Actual Problems of Economics*, 130, 13-20. <https://s3.amazonaws.com>

60. Romaniuk, J., & Sharp, B. (2003). Measuring brand perceptions: Testing quantity and quality. *Journal of Targeting, Measurement and Analysis for Marketing*, 11(3), 218-229. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.jt.5740079>
61. Ryu, K., Lee, H., & Gon Kim, W. (2012). The influence of the quality of the physical environment, food, and service on restaurant image, customer perceived value, customer satisfaction, and behavioral intentions. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 24(2), 200-223. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596111211206141>
62. Saleem, H., & Sarfraz Raja, N. (2014). The impact of service quality on customer satisfaction, customer loyalty and brand image: Evidence from hotel industry of Pakistan. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 16(1), 117-122. <https://doi.org/10.9790/487x-1616117122>
63. Sekaran, U. (1992). *Research methods for business: A skill-building approach*.
64. Selnes, F. (1993). An examination of the effect of product performance on brand reputation, satisfaction and loyalty. *European Journal of Marketing*, 27(9), 19-35. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090569310043179>
65. Scholz, M., Türk, B., & Berresheim, P. (2012). Measuring service quality in online luxury goods retailing. *Journal of electronic commerce research: JECR*, 13(1), 88-103.
66. Shin, K., Amenuvor, F. E., Basilisco, R., & Owusu-Antwi, K. (2019). Brand Trust and Brand Loyalty: A Moderation and Mediation Perspective. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 38(4), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.9734/cjast/2019/v38i430376>
67. Swaddling, D. C., & Miller, C. (2002). Don't measure customer satisfaction. *Quality Progress*, 35, 62-67. <https://doi.org/10.1108/mbe.2002.26706dae.009>
68. Taylor, S. A., & Baker, T. L. (1994). An assessment of the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in the formation of consumers' purchase intentions. *Journal of Retailing*, 70(2), 163-178. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4359\(94\)90013-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4359(94)90013-2)
69. Thailand population (2022). *Worldometer - real time world statistics*. <https://srv1.worldometers.info/world-population/thailand-population/>
70. Tu, Y., & H. C. (2011). The effect of service quality, customer perceived value and satisfaction on loyalty. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 3(3), 198-212. <https://doi.org/10.22610/jebbs.v3i3.273>
71. Turban, E. (2000). *Electronic commerce: A managerial perspective*. Allyn & Bacon.
72. Wang, F., & Hariandja, E. S. (2016). The influence of brand ambassador on brand image and consumer purchasing decision: A case study of Tous les Jours in Indonesia. *International Conference on Entrepreneurship (IConEnt-2016) "How Innovation could Improve the Performance and Productivity in Entrepreneurship?"* Indonesia.
73. Woodruff, R. B. (1997). Customer value: The next source for competitive advantage. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 25(2), 139-153. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02894350>
74. Xie, J. & Chaipoo Pirutana, S. (2014). An Examination of the Influencing Factors toward Customer Satisfaction: Case study of Five Star Hotel in Bangkok, Thailand. *International Conference on Business, Law and Corporate Social Responsibility*, 21-25. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15242/ICEHM.ED1014034>
75. Yamane, T. (1973). *Statistics: An introductory analysis*. HarperCollins Publishers.
76. Yi, L. & Chaipoo Pirutana, S. (2017). A comparative study of brand loyalty toward luxury handbag between customers from Beijing and Shanghai in China. *Proceedings of KU SRC 2nd national conference 2017: Innovation and creativity for Thailand 4.0*, 462-471.
77. Yoo, J., & Jin, Y. (2013). Effects of celebrity-organization congruence on audience attitudes, preferences, and credibility ratings for goodwill ambassadors. *Asian Journal of Communication*, 23(6), 620-636. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01292986.2013.790912>
78. Zaim, S., Turkyilmaz, A., Tarim, M., Ucar, B., & Akkas, O. (2010). Measuring customer satisfaction in Turk telekom company using structural equation modeling technique. *Journal of Global Strategic Management*, 1(4), 89-89. <https://doi.org/10.20460/jgsm.2010415842>
79. Zeithaml, V. A. (1988). Consumer perceptions of price, quality, and value: A means-end model

andsynthesis ofevidence. *Journal of Marketing*,
52(3), 2. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1251446>

80. Zeithaml, V.A. & Bitner, M.J. (1996). *Service Marketing*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.